

THE IMPACT OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS ON BUSINESS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Nowadays, mobile phones change our life significantly, they have become an integral part of modern life that helps to communicate with people even from long distance and accessing the information easily. Recent statistics claimed that there are about 7,21 billion smartphone users around the world, representing approximately 90% of the world's total population. Mobile phones claimed that the most effective and communicative tools to have brought about development to every range of business or financial industry, according to Tom Standage, digital editor of the International Telecommunication Union.

For example, Kenya's m-Pesa system, which has contributed a lot to the mobile banking industry, has provided banking and payment service, and of course it has contributed a lot to the development of ICT. Moravchinski and Pliksens (2009) have explored how using M-Pesa mobile services benefits humans. For example, a businessman with a fishery in the city of Kerala sought out the most vulnerable markets through his mobile application in order to promote the trade in products, sold their products to them and achieved an 8% increase in profits in a short period of time. By this point, fish sales were falling by 4%.

New forms of business are also emerging through mobile phones, with online trading becoming increasingly accessible to all. According to a study conducted by Aker and Mbiti (2019), the use of mobile communication is also very beneficial for farmers, since they do this work through mobile phones without spending too much effort and energy, time to find a buyer by walking around the markets, and how much money they save. This is a daunting opportunity to sell to the best buyers and develop the business.

Innovations in the field of mobile phones are again contributing to the development of many industries. Through it, people can use services such as writing, voice, painting and video communication to communicate with their customers and partners, employees on the job, even if they stand at a long distance. It has also developed the use of online education, healthcare services,

food industry, and online sales. According to data provided by the World Bank, the use of mobile phones has contributed significantly to the economic growth of developing countries, improving people's living standards, generating effective business profits, and creating new jobs.

It should also be noted that the development of the mobile communications sector has also contributed to the growth of Uzbekistan's foreign trade. In addition, as a result of the ongoing reforms, about 180 services have been launched through e-government and a single portal, and costs have been significantly saved. The development of a mobile application has helped businesses attract new customers, increase their loyalty, and produce new unique products. After Covid-19, global trade has undoubtedly shifted to the field of mobile commerce. Even now, business owners are in high demand for the development of mobile applications. Because the modern consumer appreciates convenience, and mobile applications satisfy this need. In our country, mobile applications have created the opportunity to use taxis, car sharing and delivery, as well as banking services more conveniently.

Mobile applications are the easiest and most convenient way to communicate with customers in any area of business, through interaction you can provide information about products, make offers, and increase user activity. Mobile applications are also useful for employees, who can perform tasks faster and more conveniently without being tied to their workplace. The cost of the program directly depends on how much time the developers spend on it, and the more hours, the more expensive the product. These programs require investment during their use, because it is important to maintain the server and bring it to a competitive level. However, creating a mobile application for a business product does not necessarily mean that it will bring success to this business. If we think that mobile applications will definitely help in business development, then before ordering a mobile application, you need to do the following:

- calculate the budget;
- determine who to trust with the development of the application, for example, to a web studio, an independent developer or ourselves using no-code services;
- study the target audience;
- study whether competitors have applications and their success;
- determine what problems customers will solve through applications;
- choose a platform for the application.

Mobile applications help businesses make more money, and due to the unlimited geographical area, almost 5 billion people, that is, anyone with a smartphone, can become your customer. The role of mobile applications has significantly increased, as confirmed by global statistical and analytical researchers in the digital economy.

Mobile technologies have opened up new opportunities for the emergence of new types of businesses and campaigns that serve previously non-existent needs. New campaigns have emerged in Russia in this area and have become world leaders. For example, passenger transport Yandex Taxi, navigation and car displays WayRay and Hudway, mobile gaming markets MyTona and Playrix. About 18% of IT companies confirmed that the origin of these campaigns is precisely due to mobile applications, since more than half of them specialize in mobile applications, and 32% I believe that mobile technologies have become a new priority direction of development of campaigns. 70% of campaigns in traditional industries emphasize that the use of mobile technologies is an important factor in developing their business.

According to the GSMA's 2024 report "The Mobile Economy," mobile applications and services will contribute \$5.7 billion to economic growth in 2023, and the sector will create nearly 35 million jobs. In today's modern world, mobile transformation is being used in almost all sectors of the economy, including advertising, marketing, commerce, transportation, finance, courier, and healthcare. Internal business models, methods of communicating with customers and partners, and business processes are also changing. According to IDC, by 2025, 70% of the US workforce is expected to be mobile workers, meaning that employees' primary work tools will be mobile devices. In Uzbekistan, mobile applications are becoming the most convenient and effective way to do business and any other industry in the digital economy. For those who want to start their own business, we can safely say that using mobile applications will greatly help them develop their business and generate more income.

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